

How to Select the Right Law Firm

When you find yourself in a situation where you need to find a law firm, it is important to do your research and carefully select a firm rather than take your concerns to the first law firm in the phone book. Finding the right law firm can be a challenge, but it doesn't have to be an exhausting task.

1 - Determine your criteria

The first step in selecting a law firm is to make a detailed list of your needs. Law firms specialize in a number of things, from family law to FINRA arbitration. Narrow down your search by looking specifically for firms that handle cases similar to yours.

2 - Prepare for interviews

The law firm you choose will work for you, so you have the right to ask as many questions as you'd like. Once you have set up an appointment, write down questions you need to ask and leave room for taking notes during your interview with the lawyer.

3 - Compare data

Once you have notes from several law firms that meet your needs, it's time to compare them to each other. You can do this simply by writing the pros and cons on a sheet of paper or create spreadsheets with the data you have collected. If you do need [FINRA arbitration attorneys](#), be sure to add this company to your list.